

Bio4Comp

Idea proposed:

Encoding information using gate specific residues (GASPERS)

Matija Pečak,

M.Sc. Molecular Bioengineering

TU Dresden

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Encoding and decoding of information for parallel computing

According to instructions, encoding/decoding method is proposed, that can code/decode information about the path of 10s to potentially 100s of filaments travelling through a network. In short, the method depends on specially modified Microtubule (MT) that carries a certain charge. When MT travels through specially designed maze (modified with enzymes), certain bonds carrying a charge would be cleaved, which would affect net charge of MT. In the end, net charge of MT could be measured, and path would be determined depending on this charge.

MT modification:

First, modified MT should be prepared. MT would be constructed from a mixture of with sugar modified α/β tubulin dimmers, where sugars would be represented in different ratios (e.g. 50%, 25% 12,5%,...). This modification could be achieved by introduction of Cys/Ser residues in α/β tubulin tail, which would enable covalent binding of different sugars. Studies have confirmed that such modifications are indeed possible without affecting a structure of MT. Certain ratio of non-modified tubulin dimmers would also be required, to ensure unobstructed interaction with kinesines. To ensure correct functioning of this proposed method, we should be able to cleave each of selected sugars with highly specific enzyme that does not interfere with any other sugar in our system.

Sugars should be furthermore modified to carry + (or -) charge. That could be achieved by coupling polyion molecule to a sugar or by functionalizing of a sugar with a charge (Figure1). Same amount of opposite charge should be also attached to MT (no any molecule that does not get cleaved), to achieve initial charge neutrality and to enhance charge difference in MT after removal of some + (or -) charge

Figure1: MT modification

Chanel design:

Also, channel where MTs are travelling should be specially prepared. After each junction (gate), enzyme for specific sugar should be immobilized. That would cause the loss of some charge when MT would pass left, while different amount of charge would be lost provided MT travelled right (Figure 2). Next junction would also contain two (or more) enzymes that would again remove some specific amount of charge. As each amount of removed charge is specific, also change of charge on MT is path specific.

Figure 2: Chip design

Decoding:

Charge of MT is measured at the exit of a maze which could be achieved in real-time, using magnetic field. As ratio of sugars on MT is well planned, and each sugar can be cleaved only at one point in a maze, path of MT could be easily determined based on net charge generated on MT.

Example:

MT was prepared to contain 50% of Sugar 1, 25% of Sugar 2 and 12,5% of Sugar 3, each of them carrying equal + charge and run through 1 junction chip. On exit, we measure charge on MT.

Presuming that we get measurements for two MT (named MT1 and MT2). MT1 has 75% of initial + charge left, and MT2 has 62,5% charge left... Based on that observation we can assume that MT1 passed gates harbouring enzyme that cleaves Sugar 2, and MT3 has passed gates that cleave Sugar 3. Same principle can be applied to multiple steps.

Conclusion:

According to instructions, encoding/decoding method is proposed, that can code/decode information about the path of 10s to potentially 100s of filaments traveling through a network. Proposed method can do so with no need for either external guidance/observation of microtubule or any additional reaction (like PCR, MS,...) outside of a chip. Instead it depends on a detecting pathway specific change in charge on microtubule. This allows us to drastically reduce processing time of a chip. Additionally, method is designed in such way, that it uses relatively cheap and well known resources (sugars, sugar cleaving enzymes, ...), and does not depend on high tech equipment (lasers, MS;...) which make it easier to execute in a real-time.

Main limitations concerning data storage are amount of sugar-enzyme pairs that we can use and detection limit of charge difference. Since sugar-enzyme pairs can be found in abundance (in different databases) and also other cleavable polymers can be used instead, 100s of junctions long chip for comparison of countless MT could be prepared. Problem with detection limit of charge difference on MT could be tackled, by calculating better ratios of sugars represented on MT (instead of 50%,25%,12,5%,...). Only condition that needs to be fulfilled while choosing ratios, is that \sum (all charge)- X charge is never the same for two different X (X representing charge attached on specific sugar).